

Relationship Between Cultural ... (Ambali et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12574350>

Relationship Between Cultural Variables and Marital Stability among Couples in Cross River State, Nigeria

Ambali, Abdullateef¹

Email: ambalateef@gmail.com,

Tel: +2348032466999

Ker, Beatrice Onyi²

Email: kerbeaty@gmail.com

Tel: +2348037446363

Igbo, Happiness Ihuoma²

Email: higbo@bsum.edu.ng.

Tel: +2348065716172

¹Department of Psychology, Federal College of Education, Obudu, Cross River State

²Department of Educational Foundations, Benue State University Makurdi

Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between cultural variables (cultural background, religious affiliation and value attached to children) and marital stability among couples in Cross River State Nigeria. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The researcher sampled 400 married couples out of the total population of 49,317 registered couples in the state. Two instruments were used for the study: self-developed questionnaire titled Cultural Variables Questionnaire (SCVQ) and an adapted version of Marital Stability Questionnaire (MSQ). The instruments were subjected to face and content validation. Point Biserial Correlation was used to test hypothesis one while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test hypotheses two and three at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state among others. It was concluded that religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State. It was recommended amongst others that religious affiliations should not be used as a criteria for marital stability but rather, it should be used as a way of life and as a tool to breed peace in the family for the general wellbeing of the family and the society at large.

Keywords: Culture, variables, marriage, couples, stability

Introduction

Marriage is an important aspect of human society which creates identity. It is a legal and social commitment that two people (adult male and female) make to share their lives for procreation, love, companionship, security, status, religious obligations, economic consideration and conforming to social standard. Marriage as a lifelong commitment, is signified by a contract sanctioned by law for people (Animasahun & Fatile, 2011). Marriage, as an institution, is an avenue of maintaining the life-line of a people. It allows and gives the legal and social backing to individuals to come together, live together and birth the next generation of the group. In this line, social, cultural and religious tenets are passed on from one generation to the other. The individuals so joined and permitted to live as one within the community learn to live together, love their offsprings, themselves and the community.

In African tradition, separation is considered as an offense. This is supported by Arugu (2014) that within the traditional African socio-communal life, divorce is an aberration: it is neither encouraged nor accepted except in extreme situations like barrenness and incompatibility. A union without children is seen as incomplete and unfulfilled. The irony in this is that the man is encouraged to remarry while it becomes incumbent on the woman to continue in the marriage or until she is able to give birth. Consequently, more often than not, a few individuals are denied certain responsibilities, not because they are not qualified or capable of handling such but because they are not considered matured enough: they are not married. For example, in Northern Nigeria, bachelors who are seen capable of being married but not yet married are often not allowed to lead people who are married in prayers. This does not mean that God will not accept their prayers, but that they lack the

Relationship Between Cultural ... (Ambali et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12574350>

credibility of leading such prayers. Also, in taking decisions in the family, the opinions of married people are more respected than those of the unmarried (Perelli-Harris, & Styr, 2018).

Marital stability refers to the ability of a married couple to maintain their relationship over time despite challenges that may arise. Marriage is essential for humans as it helps provide the necessary support, care, and love needed for socialization and emotional wellbeing. A stable marriage provides a sense of security and emotional stability for the couple, their children, and society at large. Marital stability is crucial in shaping family dynamics, individual lives, and broader society, highlighting the need for research on factors that promote stable marriages.

Marital stability or instability do occur as a result of certain factors that may be beyond the control of the partners. This is confirmed by Ojukwu and Obiji (2016) that marital success versus marital failure relates to causal process model that provides a chain of preferences among married persons such as satisfied versus dissatisfied. More often than not, our daily social experiences show that marital failures arise from some certain behaviours or attitudes formed and exhibited by one of the married partners, which is taken as unacceptable by the other. This means that, it is the negative beliefs, knowledge, attitude and wrong perception that contribute to dissatisfaction and accusations which result into marital instability. According to Oyafunke, Falola and Salau (2014), marital stability may at times be determined by certain cultural variables including religious affiliations, cultural background and value attached to children among others.

Religion is defined by Yelnick and Danahy (2021) as the entire collection of beliefs, values, and practices that a group holds to be the true and sacred. A group's religious beliefs explain where the people fit in relation to the universe and how they should behave while here on Earth.. Couples who acknowledged a divine purpose in their marriage are more likely to collaborate, to have greater marital adjustment, and to perceive more benefits from marriage. Religious beliefs concerning relational values (for example forgiveness, commitment and sacrifice) appear to indirectly improve marriage stability and quality and beliefs about the sanctification of marriage may help married couples resolve conflict by preventing conflict, improving conflict resolution and enhancing relationship reconciliation (Nathaniel & David, 2016).

Considering the relationship between religion and marital stability, Aman, Abbas, Nurunnabi and Bano, (2019) looked at the relationship of religiosity and marital stability and found out that religious commitment and religious practice are vital for a happy married life. The findings help explain the social dynamics of marital satisfaction in Pakistani culture. Also, Skipper (2016) researched on the role of religious coping in the marital stability of strong, African American couples: A Strengths-Focused Approach and findings revealed that each of the couples interviewed self-identified as highly religiously involved and utilized religion as a source of coping and it aided marital stability among couples.

Cultural background is the context of one's life experience as shaped by membership in groups based on ethnicity, race, socioeconomic status, gender, exceptionalities, language, religion, sexual orientation, and geographical area. It incorporates all beliefs, values, stereotypes, and rules, characterizing the members of a society and differentiating it from other societies. Iriogbe (2015) asserted that the cultural background of the couples is a very strong determinant of marriage stability. He stressed that in Nigeria, cultural background and affiliation of couples could determine how they relate to each other, find solutions to common marital issues which when handled early and appropriately will minimize distress in the family. He added that couples who hail from same cultural background and possibly speak the same dialect will blend better due to similarities in ways of approaching family matters.

Determining the relationship between cultural background and marital stability, Odunayo and Oyewole (2019) investigated the influence of traditional marriage customs and cultural background on marital stability among married people in Yoruba ethnic group and the finding revealed that there exists a significant relationship between variables of traditional marriage customs and marital stability among Yoruba. Similarly, Tandi and Osarhemen (2020) investigated influence of spousal ethnicity and locus of control on marital instability of post-graduate students in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. finding from this research showed that students with intra-ethnic spouse reported significantly lesser level of marital instability than those from inter-ethnic marriage.

Moreover, in Nigeria and Africa generally, it appears that one of the foundations upon which stable marriage is built is ability for couples to have children with the desired sex of children. Among the most important social goods produced by the institution of marriage (of a man and a woman) are children. Child is a person given birth to, son or daughter, a person who hasn't yet grown up, someone inexperienced in a certain thing or someone behaving in an immature manner. Marriage does not only define the social status of people in the society, it also proves to be a most effective way of transforming a man into a husband/father and a woman into a wife/mother and ensures a child might know and be cared for by his/her biological parents. For most modern people, getting married and having children are principal life events that mark the passage into mature adulthood (Stephen & Sunday, 2017).

Relationship Between Cultural ... (Ambali et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12574350>

To ascertain the relationship between value attached to children and marital stability, Igbolo and Gyong (2014) investigated male preference and marital stability in Cross River State, South - South Nigeria and it was also found that preference for male children was mostly expressed by the female participants, with the major reason being the stability of their marriage. Similarly, Obiyo (2016) investigated the impact of childlessness on marriage and found out that children are the uniting link in the rhythm of life guaranteeing the continuation of the family from one generation to the next.

Statement of the Problem

Marriage is expected to be comfortable and stable as ordained by God but the researcher observed that many marriages are not following the religious injunction thus, marital instability (divorce, separation and remarriage) are common phenomena across globe, in Nigeria and particularly in Cross River State. Despite efforts being made by marriage counsellors, churches, mosques, among others to curb this menace, stakeholders are at a loss on the options available for identifying the causes of this situation in their attempt to proffer solutions. Many couples continue to experience turbulence in their marriages manifested in fighting, quarrelling, suspicion, unhappiness and even separation and divorce.

Given that cultural values, beliefs, and practices are often integral components of an individual's identity, it stands to reason that such variables could potentially shape one's expectations and experiences within the context of a marriage. However, the researcher observed that some marriages in Cross River State are peaceful and stable. It is against this background, that this study investigated whether cultural variables such as religious affiliation, cultural background and value attached to children correlate with marital stability among couples in Cross River State, Nigeria. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between cultural variables and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between cultural variables and marital stability of couples in Cross River State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability of couples.
2. Determine whether cultural background has relationship with marital stability of couples or not
3. Ascertain whether value attached to children has relationship with marital stability among couples or not

Research Questions

The following research question were posed to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability of couples?
2. What is the relationship between cultural background and marital stability of couples?
3. What is the relationship between value attached to children and marital stability of couples?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.
2. There is no significant relationship between cultural background and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.
3. There is no significant relationship between value attached to children and marital stability of couples in Cross River State.

Methodology

Correlational survey design was used to determine the relationship between socio-cultural variables and marital stability of couples in Cross River State. This design is justified by the fact that the purpose of the study is to establish the relationship that exists between the independent variables which are cultural factors (religious affiliation, cultural background and value attached to children) and the dependent variable which is marital stability among married couples in Cross-River State.

The population for the study comprises 49,317 registered couples in 18 Local Government Areas in the three (3) Senatorial District of Cross River State, which consist of all married spouses in Cross River State (Marriage Registry of the 18 Local Government Headquarters, Cross River State, 2020). A total of 400 married persons were selected for the study using the Glenn (2012) formula for sample size determination. In determining the sample size, the researcher considered all the Local Government areas in the three Senatorial Districts. A total of 210 couples were selected from the South, 110 couples from Central and 80 couples from the North making a total of 400 married persons through the process of convenient

Relationship Between Cultural ... (Ambali et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12574350>

sampling technique. By convenient sampling, the researcher sampled the participants in the different Senatorial Districts at his convenience and ensured that all the Local Government are represented in the sample.

Two instruments were used for the study which include: self-developed questionnaire titled: Cultural Variables Questionnaire (CVQ) and an adapted version of Marital Stability Questionnaire (MSQ). For the reliability of the instrument, the questionnaires were administered on 50 married persons. Both questionnaires yielded split-half reliability coefficient .620 and Cronbach's Alpha .850 were reported accordingly for the study. The instruments were subjected to face and content validity by three experts: One in Measurement and Evaluation, another one in Guidance and Counselling, and one in Educational Psychology; from the Department of Educational Foundations, Benue State University. Point Biserial Correlation were used to test hypothesis one and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to test hypothesis two and three at 0.05 level of significance

Results

This section handles the hypotheses that were formulated for the purpose of this study.

Hypothesis One: Religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state. This hypothesis was tested using Point Biserial correlation and the result is presented in table 2.

Table 1: Point Biserial Correlation showing the Relationship between Religious Affiliation and Marital Stability of Couples in Cross River State

		Spousal Communication	Marital Stability
Religious Affiliation	Pearson Correlation	1	.026
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.608
	N	400	400
Marital Stability	Pearson Correlation	.026	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.608	
	N	400	

Data in table 1 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .026 at $p = .608 > .05$ [$r(398) = .026; p > .05$]. Since $p .608$ is greater than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis which stated that 'religious affiliation has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state' was therefore retained. This implies that there is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability among couples in Cross River State.

Hypothesis Two: Cultural background has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and the result is presented in table 3.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the Relationship between Cultural Background and Marital Stability of Couples in Cross River State

		Cultural Background	Marital Stability
Cultural Background	Pearson Correlation	1	.678**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Marital Stability	Pearson Correlation	.678**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	

**** Correlation is Significant at .001 (2-tailed)**

Data in Table 2 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .678 at $p = .000 < .05$ [$r(398) = .678; p < .05$]. Since $p .000$ is less than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis which stated that 'cultural background has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State was therefore reject. This implies that there is a significant positive relationship between cultural background and marital stability among couples in Cross River State.

Hypothesis Three: Value attached to children has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in Cross River State. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the result is presented in table 4.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the Relationship between Values Attached to Children and Marital Stability of Couples in Cross River State

		Value Attached to Children	Marital Stability
Values Attached to Children	Pearson Correlation	1	.259**

Relationship Between Cultural ... (Ambali et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12574350>

	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Marital Stability	Pearson Correlation	.259**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	

**** Correlation is Significant at .001 (2-tailed)**

Data in Table 3 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .259 at $p = .000 < .05$ [$r(398) = .259; p < .05$]. Since $p .000$ is less than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis which stated that value attached to children has no significant relationship with marital stability of couples in cross river state was therefore reject. This implies that there is a significant relationship between value attached to children and marital stability among couples in Cross River State.

Discussion of Finding

The findings are discussed hypothesis by hypothesis as follows;

The finding in hypothesis one showed that there is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and marital stability among couples in Cross River State. This means that no matter how religious couples are, it has nothing to do with their marital stability especially if they are not willing to work on their marriage particularly in Cross River State. This study finding goes against that of Aman, et al (2019) who looked at the relationship of religiosity and marital satisfaction with the role of religious commitment and practices on marital satisfaction among Pakistani respondent and found out that religious commitment and religious practice strengthened and promoted marital satisfaction thereby strengthening marital stability. This assertion was advanced earlier by Skipper (2016) who researched on the role of religious coping in the marital stability of strong, African American couples and found that while religious affiliations may be a factor in marital stability in other cultures, most part of the world do not see religion as a way of strengthening their humanity relationship and this is applicable to marital stability. This finding is contrary to some other findings because none of them apply to this area of study. In the area of study, religion has nothing to do with marital endurance therefore couples feel that they can be committed religiously but not on marital ground.

Result in hypothesis two showed that there was a significant relationship between cultural background and marital stability among couples in Cross River State. This means that the more people cling to their cultural values, the more their level of marital satisfaction as most of the cultures have strong marital values, some with deities where people are most of the times afraid of not necessarily for the sake of marriage but for the fear of their traditional values. This finding is consistent with that of Odunayo and Oyewole (2019) who investigated the influence of traditional marriage customs and cultural background on marital stability among married people in Yoruba ethnic group and found that there exists a significant relationship between variables of traditional marriage customs and marital stability among Yoruba as the cultural and traditional values and customs significantly contribute to marital stability. This is also in agreement with Tandi and Osarhemen (2020) who investigated influence of spousal ethnicity and locus of control on marital instability of post-graduate students in the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. And found out that students with intra-ethnic spouse reported significantly lesser level of marital instability than those from inter-ethnic marriage.

Result in hypothesis three showed that there is a significant relationship between value attached to children and marital stability among couples in Cross River State. This is an implication that the more couples attach values to children in marriage, the more they are satisfied if they have children. But in events where there are no children, values attached to children may create some level of instability in the marriage among couples. The finding agrees with Igbolo and Gyong (2014) who investigated male preference and marital stability in Cross River State, South - South Nigeria and also found that preference for male children was mostly expressed by the female participants, with the major reason being the stability of their marriage. This finding is consistent with that of Obiyo (2016) who investigated the impact of childlessness on marriage: a study of married couples in Lowa community, Imo State Nigeria. The study found that for the Lowa people, children are the uniting link in the rhythm of life guaranteeing the continuation of the family from one generation to the next indicating that most of the cultures and traditions attach much values to children and if there are no children in the marriage, there could be problems.

Conclusion

On the basis and strength of the findings of this study, it is concluded that no matter how religious couples are, it has nothing to do with their marital stability especially if they are not willing to work on their marriage particularly in Cross River State.

Relationship Between Cultural ... (Ambali et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12574350>

The more people cling to their cultural values, the more their level of marital satisfaction as most of the cultures have strong marital values, some with deities where people are most of the times afraid of not necessarily for the sake of marriage but for the fear of their traditional values. It can also be concluded that the more couples attach values to children in marriage, the more they are satisfied if they have children. But in events where there are no children, values attached to children may crease some level of instability in the marriage among couples

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Religious affiliations should not be used as a criteria for marital stability but rather, it should be used as a way of life and as a tool to breed peace in the family for the general wellbeing of the family and the society at large.
2. Cultural background has been found by the researcher to be a significant tool in marital stability. Couples should be counselled to have in-depth knowledge of their partner's cultures and traditions to avoid marital instability.
3. Couples should be counselled to be patience and tolerant on the account of childlessness or inability to get required sex of a child

References

- Aman, J., Abbas, J., Nurunnabi, M., & Bano, S. (2019). The Relationship of Religiosity and Marital Satisfaction: The Role of Religious Commitment and Practices on Marital Satisfaction Among Pakistani Respondents. *Journal of behavioural science*, 9(30), 23-48
- Animasahun, R. A & Fatile, E. A (2011). Patterns of marital instability among married couples in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of African studies and development* 18 (3), 65–81.
- Arugu, L. (2014). Social indicators and effects of marriage divorce in African societies. *Journal of business and retail management* 4 (2), 2047-2854
- Gage, A. J., & Thomas, N. J. (2016). The relationship between child investment and couple relationships: A review. *Child Development Perspectives*, 10(1), 11-16.
- Glenn, D.I. (2012). *Determining sample size*. IFAS: University of Florida
- Igbolo, M. A. & Gyong, J. E (2014). Male reference and marital stability in Cross River State, South South Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 19 (10) 17-24
- Iriogbe L. 2015 Cultural factors and family background as correlates of marital success in Warri Metropolis (Unpublished M.Ed Dissertation)
- Nathaniel, M.L & David, C.D (2016). How religiosity helps couples prevent, resolve, and overcome marital conflict. *Journal of family relation*. 55(4)439-449
- Obiyo, I. D. (2016). Impact of Childlessness on Marriage. (A Study of Married Couples in Lowa Community, Imo State). *International Journal of Religious and Cultural Practice* 2(1) 2579-0501.
- Ogunayo, A.O & Oyewole, O.O. (2019). Traditional marriage customs and marital stability among married people in Yoruba ethnic group. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 2 (4), 23-27
- Ojukwu, M.O. and Obiji, D. (2016). Effect of socio-psychological factors on marital stability of married persons in Imo State Nigeria. *Research Journal of Humanities and Cultural Studies*, 2(1), pp.1-10.
- Oyafunke-Omoniyi, C., Falola, H. O & Salau, O. P (2014) *Effect of marital instability on children in Abeokuta Metropolis*. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*, 2 (3), 68-77.
- Perelli-Harris, B., & Styrc, M. (2018). Mental well-being differences in cohabitation and marriage:

Relationship Between Cultural ... (Ambali et. al., 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12574350>

The role of childhood selection. *Journal of marriage and the family*, 80(1), 239–255.

Pourmovahed, Z., Mahmoodabadi, H. Z., Ardekani, S. M. Y., Fallahzadeh, H., Tavangar, H., & Mahmoodabad, S. S. M. (2018). Validation of the family stability questionnaire in married couples: a confirmatory factor analysis. *Electronic Physician*. 10 (8) 7185-7195

Skipper, A. D. (2016). The role of religious coping in the marital stability of strong, African American couples: A strengths-focused approach. *LSU Doctoral Dissertations*. 169. Retrieved on 30th November, 2021 from https://digitalcommons.lsu.edu/gradschool_dissertations/169

Tandi, L. I., & Osarhemen, S. F. (2020). Influence of Spousal Ethnicity and Locus of Control on Marital Instability of Post-Graduate Students. *International Journal of Innovative Psychology & Social Development* 8(4):9-14.

Yelnick, J. and Danahy, K (2021). What is religious belief? - Definition & systems. Retrieved on 7th December, 2021 from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-religious-belief-definition-systems-quiz.html>